

EFFECT OF QUALITY CUSTOMER DRIVEN SERVICES ON THE PERFORMANCE OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN OKELEWO, ABEOKUTA, OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Consistently consistent profit has been recognized as a pertinent enabler of financial stability, growth, and return on investment and survival of deposit money banks globally. These profits are viewed as critical to the survival of financial services operating milieu and deposit money banks are expected to maintain profitability while conducting their banking operations. However, deposit money bank's profitability has been on the decline as evidenced by economic meltdown, capital inadequacy, high operating expenses, thinning earnings, poor risk management, intense competition and absence of modern technology. These challenges have continued to attract the attention of scholars and policymakers. Existing literature indicates that quality customer driven services is suggestive of addressing these challenges. Therefore, this study investigated the effect of quality customer driven services on the profitability of selected deposit money banks in Okelewo, Abeokuta, Ogun State. Survey research design was adopted. Stratified random sampling method was used in selecting the respondents. Validated questionnaire was administered for data collection. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics such as multiple and hierarchical linear regression. Findings revealed that quality customer driven services had a significant effect on profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study concluded that quality customer driven services affect the profitability of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study recommended that government and deposit money banks should lock-in to enhance customer experience, drive bank-wide profitability and promote financial inclusion in Nigeria.*

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1.0 Introduction

Globalization, technological advancement and worldwide trade liberalisation has affected organizational structures, practices and the banking sector which made it imperative for government, policy formulators and top management of banks to have a paradigm shift about the way things are done. In this context, deposit money bank services have undergone rapid transformation and reengineering across the world as a result of the notable gamut of challenges prevalent in their operating milieu. One of the ways by which banks can meet the expectations of their customers is by consistently striving to provide niche quality customer-driven services (Oluwasanya, 2025). In a mixed economy like that of Nigeria, there are surplus (savers, haves) and deficit (users, have-nots) economic units (Oluwasanya, 2025). The primary function of banks is to mobilize funds from the surplus units (savers, haves) by means of deposits and channel them to the deficit units (users, have-nots) (mostly top-tier entrepreneurs, high-end corporates etc.) by means of loans and advances (Oluwasanya, 2025). These pertinent financial intermediation roles are necessary lubricant that oils the wheel of economic growth, and poverty reduction Nigeria-wide (Oluwasanya, 2025). There is no doubt that the performance of deposit money banks is crucial to the financial stability and economic growth of nations (Ademilua et al., 2025). The banking sector's profitability has

been impacted by thinning income streams and high operational costs, with global non-performing loan ratios reaching 3.8% in 2023 (World Bank, 2023). In tandem with significant challenges that manifest unpleasant service quality dimensions such as service reliability, service responsiveness, service assurance, service empathy, and service tangibles. In America, banks are witnessing a decline in profit levels from 2023 to 2025 largely due to thinning interest margins, increased credit costs and economic uncertainty. Also, aggregate net profit reduced by 11% year on year in second quarter 2025. Notably, Wells Fargo net interest income by 8% in first quarter 2025. Non-performing loan ratio was 1.5% as at September, 2025. In United Kingdom, bank's profit levels reduced from 2023 to 2025, particularly due to slower loan growth, rising loan delinquencies, lower interest rates, compressing interest margins and regulatory pressures. Notably, UK's five largest lenders saw a 9% decline in pre-tax profit in the first to third quarter of 2025 compared to the same period in 2023. Specifically, Lloyds bank's profit in first quarter of 2024 declined to 1.7 billion pounds from 2.3 billion pounds in first quarter 2023. Also, Natwest operating pre-tax profit in first quarter of 2024 declined to 1.2 billion pounds from 1.8 billion pounds in first quarter 2023. Similarly, Barclays bank pre-tax profit in first quarter of 2024 declined to 2.2 billion pounds from 2.6 billion pounds in first quarter 2023. Non-performing loan ratio was

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1.0% (World Bank, 2024). In India, banks profit levels have declined due to narrowing margins and increased credit costs. Aggregate net profit declined by 11% with quarterly declines for several banks including IndusInd Bank (70%), SBI (20%), ICICI Bank (11%) and HDFC (6%). African banks, particularly in Nigeria, witnessed a decline in profit levels from 2023 to 2025. Nigerian banks profit before taxation dropped by 19.2% in 2025 with pre-tax return on average equity plummeting to 27.3% from 48.2% in 2024. This decline is largely attributed to lower foreign currency revaluation gains, increased impairment charges and rising operational costs. Notably, First bank profit fell by 13% to N458.1 billion in the third quarter of 2025, Access holdings profit declined by 2.2% to N447.5 billion. Zenith bank earnings fell by 41% to N300 billion while GTCO pre-tax profit fell by 41% to N300 billion. The Central Bank of Nigeria set a new capital base requirements for banks according to their type of license on March 28, 2024. It follows therefore that banks are required to increase their capital base by March 31, 2026. However, as at November 2025, only 16 banks have met these new capital requirements while 27 others have raised capital through various means. The measure was introduced so as to enhance the resilience of the banking sector and stimulate economic growth. Most importantly, to remain competitive, deposit money banks designed various products and modus operandi so as to consistently render niche quality customer driven services Nigeria-wide. Quality

Service is an important determinant of customer loyalty due to the fact that loyal customers are a critical source of profitability to the banking business (Oluwasanya, 2025). Also, in the words of Liu et al., 2022, service quality is important for a successful service as assessment for service quality is of thorough evaluations of whether service can meet or exceed customers' expectations. This is especially important as the customer base has more leverage over the reviews and social media and thus the opinion of the customer is more educated so it becomes more difficult to bend without stellar service (Liu et al., 2022). In such a complex interaction of many factors there are a number of factors that make up service quality: tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy (Emon & Khan, 2025). Service quality is related to customer loyalty not only because of traditional aspects of service quality but also a result of an entirety of the client experience. According to Jayawardena et al. (2023), the engagement between both customers and service provider happens with tangible elements of service quality like physical environment, facilities and amenities, which constitute the first of the first set of engagement between customers and service provider. But the attaining experiential factors including staff commitment, their attitude and ability to meet and exceed customer's expectations are undoubted in creating a positive customer experience (Oluwasanya, 2025). There is a strong consensus as to the pertinence of quality customer driven

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service in engendering customer loyalty; however, the relationship between them is complex and multifaceted (Oluwasanya, 2025). A number of factors (such as the type of the service provided, the demographics of the target audience, external factors including economic conditions and societal trends) can influence the correlation between satisfaction and loyalty (Chen et al., 2022). The service quality expectations and perceptions may also depend on regional inequalities. For some cultures, the major factor is amiability and attentiveness of the staff, and for others it is the thing that factors in cleanliness, operational efficiency (Emon & Khan, 2024). Thus, in the context of banking business, the determinants of customer loyalty denote bespoke relationship management and tailored solutions towards customer satisfaction (Oluwasanya, 2025).

2.0 Statement of the Problem

Globally, quality customer driven service is recognized as pertinent enabler of consistently consistent profitability by deposit money banks. The benefits of quality customer driven services are multifarious, including service excellence, steady income streams, competitive edge, improved image, customer loyalty, customer satisfaction. Despite the benefits of quality customer driven services, deposit money banks have struggled to apply quality service strategies into visible and unvarying service niche. This underscores the need for effective and efficient quality customer driven services to permeate and percolate the comity of deposit money banks

Nigeria-wide. However, the Nigerian operating precinct presents numerous challenges that vitiates the efficiency and effectiveness of quality customer driven service delivery by deposit money banks. These challenges include capital inadequacy, thinning income, high operational costs, technological gaps, defective employee training and development, changing customer's needs, porous quality control and assurance and regulatory constraints, A significant challenge facing quality service delivery include outdated technology, cyber security threats, inadequate service enablers, digital literacy gaps by customers and critical skill gaps by the service person in deposit money banks (Oluwasanya, 2025). In the words of Aharon et al. (2021), customers who perceived high service quality are more likely to share and contribute to the brand's success. Has shown. Moreover, the dynamics between service quality and customer loyalty is influenced by evolution of expectations and behaviour of the customer (Emon et al., 2024). Several researchers, including Ojiaku et al. (2023) and Omofowa et al. (2021), have identified critical gaps in the literature regarding the specific impact of service quality dimensions on bank performance in the Nigerian context while Oluwasanya (2025) posited that effective application of service strategy engenders service niche and competitive edge. Research conducted by Nguyen et al. (2020) and Dahal (2022) have established strong correlations between service quality and bank performance in other markets, the unique challenges of the Nigerian banking

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sector require targeted investigation. Also, Oluwasanya, (2025) posited that meeting and exceeding customer's expectations will only be sustainable if the appropriate service strategy for niche service delivery is prevalent. Several studies have examined the effect of service quality on profitability in developed countries, highlighting the critical role of service excellence in driving performance in various sectors (Ahmed & Bhatti, 2019; De Leon et al., 2020; Islam et al., 2020; Mostafa, 2020; Raza et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2023). These studies have demonstrated how superior service quality leads to increased customer satisfaction, loyalty, and ultimately enhanced profitability through repeat patronage and referrals (Oluwasanya, 2025). However, there is limited research investigating the effect of service quality dimensions of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangibles on profitability in developing countries particularly in the Nigerian deposit money banks (Abror et al., 2020; Aigie et al., 2023; Kaigama & Kachalla, 2023; Olalekan et al., 2019; Onyia et al., 2022; Osiegbu & Onuorah, 2018; Usman et al., 2023). Therefore, this study aims to investigate the effect of quality customer driven services on the profitability of selected deposit money banks in Okelewo, Abeokuta, Ogun State, South-West, Nigeria, addressing a critical knowledge gap in the existing literature.

3.0 Literature Review

Quality customer-driven service is about strategic thinking and economic warfare tailored to out-perform competitors (other deposit

money banks) in the art of service delivery. The market place is the battlefield, the competitors are the enemy and the price for the victors of this economic warfare is increased income streams, productivity, image and profitability (Oluwasanya, 2025). The main objectives of quality customer-driven strategy are to create a niche, which is observable or measurable and perceived by customers. The service strategy must be a central part of the company's business strategy, which will also cover profit objectives, markets, technology and so on. it is central because it defines the company's internal dynamics as well as its desired image. t needs to be evidenced in writing and communicated widely, so that no one is in doubt about what it is designed to achieve. It needs to be matched by organization structure designed for customer response. The strategy must include customers' unmet needs and expectations, benchmarking competitors' activities because without knowledge of what your main competitors are doing, it is impossible provide outperforming services that will stimulate repeat patronage and customer satisfaction. This evaluation of service delivery will reveal gaps, (areas that needs to be addressed) and strategies will be put in place to address such identified service gaps. If the identified gaps are effectively addressed, it will trigger quantum leap improvements in the quality, speed, efficiency and effectiveness of service delivery and it will also contribute to the field of quality customer driven services in tandem with customer's perception of the

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efficacy of service delivery bankwide (Oluwasanya, 2025). Plethora of studies on quality service delivery by deposit money banks over the recent decades has consistently indicated the vital impact of quality service on customer satisfaction in order to engender repeat patronage. In deposit money banks, survival depends on a tacit understanding of the factors influencing quality of service and its effect on profitability. According to Oluwasanya, (2025) quality customer-driven service is the differentiating factor that sustains competitive edge in the market place. He posited further that the application of key quality service indicators such as speed, quality, efficiency and effectiveness engenders increased profitability. Emon & Khan, (2024) defined quality service as the amount of fulfilment or exceedance of service provider towards service client expectations. Service quality is the degree to which the specific functionalities or features of a service satisfy customer requirements (Ogbeide et al., 2023). Ojiaku et al. (2023) referred to service quality is the customer's overall impression and assessment of a service, gauging the difference between their expectations and their actual experience across interactions with the service provider. Service quality refers to the effectiveness of a service in fulfilling its intended functions, operationally defined by metrics such as response times, error rates, and customer complaint resolution (Sultana & Taher, 2023). Service quality is the totality of a customer's service experience, considering emotional,

sensory, and functional aspects (Li et al., 2021). Hariawan et al. (2021) defined service quality as the ability of a service to adapt and respond to the unique needs and preferences of individual customers. According to Uwabor et al. (2021), service quality is the degree to which a service meets or exceeds customer expectations, influenced by the perception of value and satisfaction the customer receives in exchange for their investment of time, money, and effort. Endara et al. (2019) define service quality through key dimensions such as reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and responsiveness that together shape customer perceptions of a service provider's ability to meet their needs. Quality service has been evaluated by dimensions such as reliability, assurance, tangibility, empathy and responsiveness (Emon, 2025). It follows therefore that Nigerian banks can be described as product or sales-driven rather than market or customer-driven (Oluwasanya, 2025). In view of the above opinions in literature, the researchers define service quality as the degree to which a service meets or exceeds customer expectations, influenced by the perception of value and satisfaction the customer receives in exchange for their investment of time, money and effort. Research conducted by Ademilua et al., (2025) on the effect of service quality dimensions on profitability of selected deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study concluded that service quality dimensions improved the profitability of the selected deposit money banks in Lagos State,

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Nigeria. In a related study by Odere and Abugu (2025) on assessing the effect of service quality on customer's patronage of deposit money banks in Enugu state, Nigeria. The study found that service assurance, reliability and empathy respectively exert significant positive effect on customers' patronage of deposit money banks in Enugu State, Nigeria. A study by Fatoki, (2021) on the impact of banking service on customer satisfaction in Nigerian banking sector. Findings revealed that customer satisfaction is a key performance indicator in the banking industry and customers' satisfaction has great influence on profitability of banks. Researchers such as Osiegbu and Onuorah (2018) conducted a study on service quality delivery and deposit money bank's performance in Nigeria. The study found that there is a positive relationship between service quality delivery and the earnings of deposit money banks. In a study by Ocheke et al., (2017) on analysis of effective customer service satisfaction on Nigerian profitability: a queuing and regression analysis in Sokoto metropolis. It was revealed that the level of speed in transaction significantly affect bank's profitability and performance. Research conducted by Ekechukwu, (2016) on evaluating customer service on organizational profitability in zenith bank plc: a study of Enugu metropolis. The study established that there is positive effect relationship between effective communication to clients and product sales of the bank. While a study by Farayibi, (2016) on service delivery and customer satisfaction in Nigerian banks. The

study concluded that effective customer service delivery significantly affects customer satisfaction. In a study by Olusanya and Oluwasanya (2014) on information technology and banking services: synergy that drives niche quality customer driven services in Nigerian banks. Findings revealed that information technology significantly influence the efficiency and effectiveness of service delivery by Nigerian banks. As pointed out by Carvalho and Alves (2022), the physical characteristics of the service environment, such as cleanliness, pleasant aesthetics are determining factors for customer satisfaction that positively determine repeat patronage and word of mouth referrals. Lewis and Booms (1983) define Quality Service as a measure of how well the services rendered meets the expectations of customers. The areas of expectations constitute dimensions of quality service. The SERVQUAL model was developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry (1988, 15) to identify five different gaps between customers expectation and service that is provided by a company. This study measured service quality by tangibility, assurance, reliability, responsiveness and empathy. The dimensions are discussed hereunder:

Tangibility: refers to aspects of personnel, equipment and physical facilities. Tangibles are physical indicators that contribute to a customer's perception of a service or product's value (Redda & Van Deventer, 2023). Tangibles are the physical evidence of a service, process, or commitment (Lim et al., 2023). Kemkamma and

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Gladson-Nwoka (2023) further highlight that service tangibles are influenced by factors such as the organization's branding, the cleanliness and organization of the physical environment, and the professional attire and grooming of employees. According to Do et al. (2021), tangibles can be defined as physical elements that are perceived through the senses, providing material proof or representation. Tangibles are concrete manifestations that represent the quality or presence of a service or product (Subiyantoro, 2021). Tangibles are material items that help represent abstract concepts, like brand quality or service standards (Sheikh et al., 2021). Tangibles are quality cues that customers perceive through visual, tactile, or other sensory feedback (Tohid et al., 2021). Tangibles are elements that provide evidence of the quality or reliability of an organization (Fauzi et al., 2021). Tangibles are visible indicators that reflect the quality or reliability of a service or organization (Goyit & Nmadu, 2020).. Khatoon et al. (2020) referred to tangibles as the physical aspects of a service that contribute to the overall customer experience. According to Khalil et al. (2020), the key characteristics of service tangibles include the physical facilities, equipment, and appearance of personnel that customers experience during the service encounter. Tangibles encompass the physical environment where a service is provided, such as furniture, lighting, and layout (Hoang, 2018). In this study, tangibles denote bank locatable place of service, accessibility, speed and efficiency of service,

external appearance and interior comfort and finally, staff appearance and neatness.

Assurance: According to Patel et al., (2024) assurance is the consistency of a product's performance, inspiring confidence over time. Assurance is the commitment to protecting customer interests by ensuring the quality and reliability of a service (Garba et al., 2023). Assurance is the confidence that a particular outcome is predictable and aligned with expectations (Tam, 2023). Assurance is a guarantee that the quality of a product or service will meet or exceed expectations (Wang et al., 2023). Assurance is the promise that a service, product, or process will perform consistently over time (Ojiaku et al., 2023). Assurance is the process of validating that expectations and standards will be met (Kankam, 2023). Assurance is the process of taking measures to mitigate risks, ensuring dependable outcomes (Samuel et al., 2023). Assurance involves taking actions to reduce risks within operations, providing confidence in outcomes (Jasin & Firmansyah, 2023). Nautwima and Asa (2022) referred to assurance as the verification that quality standards have been met consistently. According to Agrawal et al. (2022), assurance is the dependability of standards that uphold quality across various conditions. Assurance is the process of reducing uncertainty by confirming the reliability or validity of an outcome (Dahal, 2022). Nguyen and Nguyen (2021) defined assurance as the confidence based on evidence or proven performance. In

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this study, Assurance entails service assurance as the ability of an organization to instill confidence and trust in customers through the competence, professionalism, and reliability of its services and personnel.

Reliability: In the words of Oluwasanya, (2025) reliability is the degree to which a system or individual can be trusted to consistently perform its assigned roles and responsibilities efficiently and effectively. Reliability is the extent to which a person can be depended upon to perform tasks with precision and responsibility (Shahabuddin et al., 2024). Patel et al. (2024) posited that reliable services can improve employee morale, reduce operational costs, and free up resources for innovation and strategic initiatives. Reliability measures the extent to which services are offered accurately and on timely manner by staff of a bank. Tien and Huong (2023) referred to reliability as the degree to which an outcome or service meets the expectations set by the user or customer without failure. Yoeung et al. (2023) emphasize that high levels of service reliability can lead to increased customer satisfaction, loyalty, and positive word-of-mouth. Nautwima and Asa (2022) posited that reliable services can also enhance an organization's reputation, competitive advantage, and ability to attract new customers. Reliability is the degree to which repeated measurements yield consistent, dependable results (Anh, 2022). According to Anyadighibe et al. (2022), reliability is the high level of confidence that users or customers have in the performance of a system or service.

Reliability is the level of trust placed in an entity's ability to fulfill its responsibilities without deviation or error (Karmacharya, 2022). Olalekan et al. (2019) defined reliability as the consistency and dependability of a system, process, or individual to perform its intended function over time. Aspects of reliability in this study include Prompt service delivery, Provision of wide range of value added products, security of transactions and customer information and finally, Performing services accurately and dependably.

Responsiveness: In banking parlance, responsiveness signifies the speed with which the service person attends to customer's grievances, problems and complaints. According to Oluwasanya (2025), responsiveness is the passion, timeliness, efficiency and effectiveness of services rendered to customers. Febriend and Qastharin (2024) posited that responsiveness is the speed and efficiency with which a person or system addresses the needs or requests of others. Sutrisno and Lazuardy (2024) pointed that responsiveness is the willingness and ability to react or reply to stimuli, needs, or changes in a timely manner. Responsiveness is the skill of prioritizing and addressing urgent needs over less immediate concerns (Khan et al., 2023). Responsiveness is the state of being instantly available to handle requests, inquiries, or emergencies as they arise (Susanto et al., 2023). Responsiveness, is the willingness to take immediate action when a problem or request is identified (Rido et al., 2023). Responsiveness is

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the degree to which a service provider prioritizes and responds promptly to customer requests and concerns (Nwagwu et al., 2023). Responsiveness is the quality of swiftly attending to customer needs to enhance satisfaction and build trust (Gonu et al., 2023). Nemneichong and Robita (2022) referred to responsiveness as the ability of a business or system to adapt rapidly to changes in market demand or competition. Responsiveness in this study encompasses willingness of staff to assist customers promptly, Answering customers' enquiries on time, Provision of correct service at the first time and Provision of fast and efficient service at the counter.

Empathy: Empathy connects emotionally to the customers and leads to customer loyalty and repeat patronage. Empathy is the passionate customer-friendly attitude and personalized service willingly and enthusiastically rendered to customers Oluwasanya (2025). Empathy is a compassionate awareness that allows one to recognize and validate the emotions of others (Ghimire & Agarwal, 2024). Rijal (2024) referred to empathy as the emotional connection that allows one person to experience the emotions of another. Empathy is the act of putting oneself in another's position to understand their thoughts and feelings (Aripin et al., 2023). Onyia et al. (2022) defined empathy as the intuition to recognize and interpret the emotions of those around us. According to Alam et al. (2022), empathy is the capacity to understand and share the feelings and perspectives of another person.

Empathy is the ability to comprehend and relate to the emotions felt by others (Anyadighibe et al., 2022). Empathy is the skill of understanding people's experiences on an emotional level (Seenivasan, 2021). Paul and Sharmila (2021) defined empathy as the identification with another person's emotional state or situation. Empathy is the ability to feel what others are feeling, creating a deep sense of connection (Ali et al., 2021). Empathy is the awareness of others' experiences, needs, and challenges (Sasono et al., 2021). In this study empathy denotes the level of individualized attention to customers, customer care, customer relationship management, courtesy and customer-friendly attitude and service delivery.

Profitability as the ability to generate consistent income streams over expenditure thereby enhancing stakeholder value (Oluwasanya, 2025). Profitability is the net gain achieved by a company after accounting for all its expenses (Ghimire & Agarwal, 2024). Beanning (2024) states that profitability also allows banks to expand their customer base and market share. Profitability is the measurable extent to which income is generated from business activities (Kemkamma & Gladson-Nwoka, 2023). Profitability is the financial success of a business, indicated by its revenue exceeding its expenses (Usman et al., 2023). Fitrio et al. (2023) referred to profitability as the ability of a company to produce income from its operations. Tien and Huong (2023) defined profitability as the capacity of a business to generate earnings

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beyond its costs over time. Susanto et al. (2023) and Al-Shorman et al. (2022) opined that profitable banks can offer more competitive products and services, attract and retain talented employees, and provide better returns to shareholders. Karmacharya (2022) defined profitability as the efficiency of generating revenue compared to the costs incurred. Profitability is a measure of a company's potential to earn revenue consistently over time (Anh, 2022). Profitability is a positive financial outcome resulting from successful business operations (Alam et al., 2022). Profitability is the amount of revenue that remains after covering all cash outflows (Onyia et al., 2022). Saraswati (2022) and Rajasulochana (2022) emphasize that high levels of bank profitability enable financial institutions to build strong capital buffers, withstand economic downturns, and invest in innovation and technology. Profitability is the ability of a business to sustain its earnings over the long term (Paul & Sharmila, 2021). Profitability, is the return achieved on resources invested in a business (Mohamed & Ishar, 2021). Profitability is the surplus generated when revenue exceeds total costs and expenses (Sasono et al., 2021). Ambarita et al., (2021) defined profitability as the return earned from the sales of products or services. Profitability is an indicator of a company's financial health and stability (Tien et al., 2021). Profitability is the sustainability of a company's revenue generation relative to its costs (Jayasree, 2021). Profitability is the degree to which a business creates wealth

for its owners or shareholders (Haron et al., 2020). Islam et al. (2020) defined profitability as the income left after deducting all business related expenses. Profitability is the effectiveness with which a business utilizes resources to generate income (Nayanajith et al., 2019). Profitability is the extent to which income exceeds the costs incurred in business operations (Olalekan et al., 2019).

Quality Service and Profitability

Various studies have examined the effect of quality service on organizational profitability. Researchers such as Sutrisno and Lazuardy (2024) and Shahabuddin et al. (2024) both revealed that service quality exerts a significant and positive influence on profitability ratios. Similarly, Febriend and Qastharin (2024) and Pratama et al. (2024) discovered that service quality has a positive and significant impact on maintaining profitable customer relationships. Supporting these positive relationships, Ifedi et al. (2024) also revealed that service quality has a significant and positive effect on profitability. Research conducted by Tresnadi et al. (2024) found that service quality dimensions positively affect profitability measures. In a study, Ghimire and Agarwal (2024) established that superior service quality significantly enhances customer satisfaction, leading to increased profitability. Khan et al. (2024) and Tam (2023) found that service quality initiatives significantly boost profit margins. Also, Susanto et al. (2023) and Bintoro et al. (2023) established that enhanced service quality leads to improved financial

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performance. Aripin et al. (2023) and Samuel et al. (2023) discovered that the significant effect of service quality on profitability is consistent across different industries while Gonu et al. (2023) showed that service quality positively influences return on investment. In a study, Endara et al. (2019) found that service quality dimensions have a substantial positive impact on financial performance metrics. Plethora of researchers have applied frameworks and models to determine the factors that influence quality service and consequently, how it affects the profitability of deposit money banks. Ifedi et al. (2024) argued that SERVQUAL is effective in identifying service areas that need improvement to positively influence customer loyalty and behavioral outcomes, further supporting the model's relevance to business performance. Abubakar et al. (2024) emphasized that SERVQUAL's five dimensions remain relevant and that its adaptability makes it particularly valuable for cross-cultural service quality assessment. Sultana and Taher (2023) highlighted SERVQUAL's adaptability across service industries, affirming that the model effectively captures key elements of customer satisfaction through a gap analysis approach.

SERVQUAL model developed by Parasuraman, Valarie Zeithaml, and Leonard Berry in 1985 was a model for service quality assessment which have five key dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. These qualities and characteristics have been strategically reengineered by scholars in the

context of the deposit money banks. Among the reasons is the intangible nature of services in the sector, which makes it considerably more difficult to measure the customer experience compared to the tangible ones. SERVQUAL model assumes that customer expectations are not static but change over time based on various factors like previous experiences, competitor offerings, and cultural influences. SERVQUAL model further assumes that the gap between expectations and perceptions exists in all service industries and can be similarly measured, regardless of the type of service being assessed (Parasuraman, 1985). The model assumes that comparing customer expectations to their actual perceptions will reveal service quality deficiencies that the provider can address (Zeithaml, 1985). Service providers must continually adapt to meet these evolving expectations (Berry, 1985). Jasneet et al. (2022) emphasized SERVQUAL's applicability and versatility, reaffirming that the model provides valuable insights into customer expectations versus perceptions and is adaptable to diverse service sectors. Critics (Islam et al., 2020; Jayasree, 2021; Karmacharya, 2022; Fitrio et al., 2023; Ositadimma & Okeke, 2019; Pratama et al., 2024; Redda & Van Deventer, 2023) argued that SERVQUAL's gap-based approach was unnecessary and suggested that service quality could be measured by perceptions alone, without comparing them to expectations. Teeroovengadum (2022) reported a negative influence, Raza et al. (2020) argued that

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SERVQUAL's use of expectations as a benchmark might be biased, as customer expectations could be influenced by unrealistic factors. Marketing theory has identified the core factors influencing customer satisfaction, particularly in the service sector, but few studies have considered the Nigerian context. This raises the question of what key factors in the SERVQUAL model influence customer satisfaction with deposit services in Nigerian banking sector. This is based on the perception that most information generated from customers

are aimed at selling more products to them instead of promoting relationships, adding value and customer satisfaction. However, SERVQUAL measurements and five gaps will help to design the questionnaire: some questions will be developed according to the gaps and dimensions mentioned above to understand customer expectations and the service that is provided. Listed hereunder is a checklists of basic quality dimensions and customer satisfaction imperatives:

Operationalization of the Variables

The study variables were categorized into three groups: Independent Variable (X): Quality customer-driven services, comprising sub-variables such as quality, speed, effectiveness, efficiency and need satisfaction. Dependent Variable (Y): Profitability, measured by revenue generation, pricing, operating expenses, customer's needs and innovation. Moderating

Variables: Banking enablers and Government Policy. The operational model for the study variables is denoted in the equations below:

$$Y = f(X)$$

$$Y = f(XZ)$$

Y= Dependent variable

X= Independent Variable

Z= Moderating Variables

Y= Profitability

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X= Quality Customer-Driven Services

Z₁ = Banking Enablers (BE) = Moderating Variable

Z₂= Government Policy (GP) = Moderating Variable

Y= (y₁, y₂, y₃, y₄, y₅)

X= (x₁, x₂, x₃, x₄, x₅)

Z= (z₁, z₂)

Where:

Y₁= Revenue Generation

Y₂ = Pricing

Y₃ = Operating Expenses

Y₄ = Customers' needs

Y₅ = Innovation

X₁ = Quality

X₂ = Speed

X₃ = Effectiveness

X₄ = Efficiency

X₅ = Need Satisfaction

Z₁ = Banking Enablers

Z₂ = Government Policy

$$y_1 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_1 = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i \text{ ----- (i)}$$

$$y_2 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_2 = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i \text{ ----- (ii)}$$

$$y_3 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_3 = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i \text{ ----- (iii)}$$

$$y_4 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_4 = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i \text{ ----- (iv)}$$

$$y_5 = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$y_5 = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i \text{ ----- (v)}$$

$$Y = f(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5)$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \beta_5x_5 + e_i \text{ ----- (vi)}$$

$$Y = f(X * Z_1)$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X + \beta_2Z_1 + \beta_3X * Z_1 + \mu_i \text{ (vii)}$$

$$Y = f(X * Z_2)$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X + \beta_2Z_2 + \beta_3X * Z_2 + \mu_i \text{ (viii)}$$

β_0 = Constant of the equation or constant term

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Parameters to be estimated

e_i = Error or stochastic term

5.0 Data Collection and Methodology

This study adopted a positivist research philosophy, which emphasized the application of natural science methods to investigate social phenomena, particularly the relationship between service quality and deposit money banks' performance. This study employed primary data collection methods to obtain raw, original and reliable information directly from respondents. The target population consisted of current account customers in the five selected deposit money banks located in Okelewo,

Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. The selected banks include Wema Bank, Stanbic-IBTC Bank, First City Monument Bank (FCMB), Access Bank and Polaris Bank (formerly Skye Bank). Based on the information obtained from the said banks, the total number of customers was 226,890 (Wema Bank 44,593; Stanbic-IBTC 27,617; FCMB 24,183 Access Bank 17,646 and Polaris Bank 12,954). A survey research design was adopted to facilitate the use of structured research instruments for data collection and analysis. This study adopted a survey research

design which examined the effect of service quality on deposit money banks' performance. According to Khan et al. (2024) and Sudirjo et al. (2024), survey research design provides a systematic approach for collecting quantitative data about service quality dimensions and their impact on bank performance metrics. This design enabled the researcher to explain and translate responses from respondents, determining the link between the dependent variable (Profitability) and the independent variable (Quality customer-driven service dimensions). The study population comprised of 226,890 current account customers from the five selected deposit money banks located in Okelewo, Abeokuta, Ogun State, Nigeria. Quota sampling technique was used to arrive at the sample size of 384 in the five banks while random sampling technique was used in administering the questionnaires among the sample subjects within the banks under study. A questionnaire was used to collect data on independent, dependent and moderating variables. Quality customer-driven services was the independent variable, with sub-variables including quality, speed, effectiveness, efficiency and need satisfaction. The dependent variable was profitability, with sub-variables including revenue generation, pricing, operating expenses, customer's needs and innovation. The instrument for measuring quality in service organisations is referred to as SERVQUAL, which was developed by Parasuraman and Zethaml (1985:1988) and adapted by Musa

(2013). This was used in generating primary data for the study. The items in the instrument reflect the four service quality areas, namely, tangibility, reliability, responsiveness and assurance measured on the five Likert scale of "Highly Satisfactory" "Fairly Satisfactory" "Satisfactory" "Unsatisfactory" and "Highly Unsatisfactory". The overall perception of quality service by the customers was measured using the five Likert scale of "Highly Positive" "Fairly Positive" "Positive" "Negative" and "Highly Negative". A structured questionnaire containing 25 items was randomly administered to 500 respondents. Out of this number only 400 (80%) were usable for the study. A structured questionnaire containing 25 items was randomly administered to 500 respondents. Out of this number only 400 (80%) were usable for the study. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data with the help of SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). To ensure the instrument's reliability, a pilot test was conducted among 35 high end corporates and top-tier customers. After two weeks, the same instrument was re-administered to assess its reliability. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient calculated using SPSS exceeded the 0.7 threshold (Asika, 2004; Biserka & Dragana, 2012).

6.0 Discussion of Findings

This study investigated the effect of quality customer driven services on the profitability of selected deposit money banks in Okelewo, Abeokuta, Ogun State, South West and Nigeria. The findings reveal that quality customer driven

services have a statistically significant influence on profitability, consistent with previous studies (Zakari et al., 2025; Saley et al., 2022; Supriyanto et al., 2021; Omofowa et al., 2021; Farayibi, A., 2016; Adekunle et al., 2013;). The study found that quality customer driven services significantly affect profitability including revenue generation, pricing, operating expenses, customer’s needs and innovation, government policy has a statistically significant moderating effect on the relationship between quality customer driven services and profitability, and the components of quality customer driven services have a positive, statistically significant effect on profitability. The study's findings suggest that quality customer driven services should be integrated into deposit money banks institution-wide, focusing on pedagogy, didactics

and content. This would enhance consistently consistent profitability by deposit money banks and stimulate the astute performance of their financial intermediation roles as the necessary lubricant that oils the wheel of progress Nigeria-wide (Oluwasanya, 2025).

Reliability

The principle component method was used for an explorative factor analysis. Three main factors with 24 items were loaded into the system. The 21 items of SERVQUAL model were factorially analyzed. According to the results, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value was .929, and Bartlett’s test of sphericity was significant at the .000 level. Table 3 reports the factor eigenvalues greater than or equal to 1.0 and variables with factor loadings greater than .5.

Table 1. Key Performance indicators of the SERVQUAL Model

Component	Assurance	Reliability	Responsiveness	Tangibility	Empathy
Item					
TA1		.882			
TA2		.824			
TA3		.769			
TA4		.763			
TA5		.734			
AS1			.790		
AS2			.775		
AS3			.671		
AS4			.637		
AS5			.602		
RS1				.842	
RS2				.720	

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RS3			.709			
RE1				.812		
RE2				.710		
RE3				.702		
EM1					.727	
EM2					.666	
EM3					.590	
Eigenvalue	6.138	2.375	1.828	1.411	1.009	
VE (%)*	32.308	12.502	9.622	7.427	5.309	
α	.888	.812	.711	.679	.695	

Total variance explained=67.166, KMO= .929, p = .000.

The factor analysis revealed five factors accounting for 67.166% of the total variance. SERVQUAL model factors were labeled as “tangibility” (32.308), “assurance” (12.502), “responsiveness” (9.622), “reliability” (7.427), and “empathy” (5.309). To test the reliability and internal consistency of each factor, its Cronbach’s alpha was determined.

According to the results, the alpha coefficients were .888 for tangible, .812 for assurance, .711 for responsiveness, .679 for reliability, and .695

for empathy. In terms of customer loyalty and satisfaction, three items were loaded. The results also, indicates that 76.363% of the total variance was explained with an eigenvalue greater than 1.0, and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin value was .722. Bartlett’s test of sphericity was significant at the .000 level. In terms of the reliability and internal consistency of factors, Cronbach’s alpha was determined to be .845 (Table 4). Cronbach’s α ranged from .888 to .679, indicating that all factors were accepted and reliable.

Table 2. Key Performance Indicators of Customer Loyalty and Satisfaction

Item	Factor loading	Eigenvalue	Total variance explained	α	KMO	Pvalue
SAT1	.894					
SAT2	.872					
SAT3	.855					
		2.291	76.363	.845	.722	.000

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Respondent Profile

Table 4: Marital Status

Table 3. Gender

<u>Age</u>	<u>Male</u>	<u>Female</u>
Below 20 years	4	9
20-29 years	71	93
30-39 years	34	48
40-49 years	50	62
50 years and above	24	5
Total	183	217

Table 5. Educational Background

<u>Marital Status</u>	<u>Male</u>	<u>Female</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Single	130	170	75
Married	53	46	24.75
Divorced	00	01	0.025
Total	183	217	100

Table 6: Occupation

<u>Education</u>	<u>Male</u>	<u>Female</u>
Elementary	0	0
Secondary	10	13
University/Polytechnic	116	159
Professional	10	18
<u>Others</u>	<u>47</u>	<u>27</u>
Total	183	217

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<u>Occupation</u>	<u>Male</u>	<u>Female</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
Civil servant	79	133	53.00
Business	61	64	31.25
Student	27	11	09.50
Others	16	9	06.25
<u>Total</u>	<u>183</u>	<u>217</u>	<u>100</u>

7.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that quality customer driven services have a significant effect on profitability of selected deposit money banks in Okelewo, Abeokuta, Ogun State, and South-West, Nigeria. The findings highlight the importance of institutionalizing and steering quality customer driven services culture and values into deposit money banks operations and services. In tandem, is need for effective government policies to support banking enablers that drives niche quality customer service delivery.

Based on the findings from the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

- Management of banks must be seized by passion to champion quality customer driven services bank-wide.
- Institutionalise with top management support, a new value system typically placing greater emphasis on meeting and exceeding customer's expectations.
- A fundamental rethink of the way service delivery gets done by streamlining and simplifying the service delivery process in

deposit money banks leading to the elimination of non-value added activities.

- Creating a more congenial and customer friendly physical oriented layout and design (aesthetically pleasing banking environment).
- Business process reengineering should be implemented by top management to fundamentally rethink and radically redesign their service operations processes and engender paradigm shift from the old ways of doing things to thinking out of the box and delivering niche customer driven quality services responsively and competently.
- Training and re-training the goose that lay the golden egg (the service person) on the values, key performance indicators and critical success factors of quality customer service delivery to engender niche performance.
- Ensure consistent and timely quality customer driven services permeates the entire work ethics of deposit money banks thereby translating into services edge, customer loyalty, respect patronage, enhanced image, earnings and bottom line.
- Private banking by providing high level of personalized and related services to elite

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clientele notably high-end corporates and high-networth individuals.

➤ Appoint relationship managers for 20% of customers of deposit money banks who accounts for 80% of the bank's revenue (80/20 Pareto Optimality rule).

➤ Improving the attitude responsiveness and customer service orientation of staffers.

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➤ Customer satisfaction survey to be completed by customers to enable feedback on complaints on service delivery gaps and customer expectations.

➤ Deposit money banks should increase their branch networks in order to increase their coverage and customers' convenience in accessing banking services.

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